

GRAPHERGIA

INNOVATIVE PILOT LINES FOR **SUSTAINABLE GRAPHENE-BASED**
FLEXIBLE AND STRUCTURAL **ENERGY** HARVESTING AND **STORAGE** DEVICES

GRAPHERGIA.EU

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POWERING THE FUTURE WITH GRAPHENE

GRAPHERGIA unites European innovators to unlock the potential of laser-assisted graphene production to shape the future of:

WITH THREE DEMO CASES

MEET THE GRAPHERGIA TEAM

GRAPHENE
FLAGSHIP

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